

Appendix 1: AR6 quantification - Data gathering and methods notebook

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Task summary

Collect stats for the 7 main reports of **IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6)**:

- the **Synthesis Report** (referred to as SYR)
- the **3 Working group reports** (referred to as WGI, WGII, WGIII)
- the **3 Special reports** (referred to as SR1.5, SRCCL, SROCC)
- **Out of scope**: the refinement to its latest Methodology Report, "2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories"

1. PDF File Size, Page count, Word count

Methods

- **File size:** from PDF file
- **Page count:** from PDF file (Page numbers + front matter pages with roman page numbers)
- **Word count:** from PDF file, copy and paste into <https://wordcounter.net/> "Basic Option", very rough estimate. Counting unreliable because I did not remove irrelevant parts of the documents, sometimes my computer's clipboard was overwhelmed with the amount of data, I also rounded the figures up or down. This definitely needs a cleaner method.

Findings

Report	File name / source	File size in MB	Approx. page count	Approx. word count
AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023 (SYR)	IPCC_AR6_SYR_FullVolume.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/	4.9	186 + 14 pages	~94.000
Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis (WG1)	IPCC_AR6_WGI_FullReport.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/	423.3	2409 pages	~1.925.000
Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability (WG2)	IPCC_AR6_WGII_FullReport.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/	396	3068 + 12 pages	~2.513.000
Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change (WG3)	IPCC_AR6_WGIII_FullReport.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/	68.8	2042 + 11 pages	~1.642.000
Special Report: Global Warming of 1.5°C (2018) (SR1.5)	SR15_Full_Report_HR.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/	65	631 pages	~511.000
Special Report: Climate Change and Land (2019) (SRCCL)	SRCCCL_Full_Report.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/	44.9	908 pages	~735.000
Special Report: The Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate (2019) (SROCC)	SROCC_FullReport_FINAL.pdf / https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/	51.9	766 pages	~627.000
Total		1054.8 MB	10047 pages	~8.047.000

2. PDF Licencing information and DOIs

Methods

- DOIs: retrieved them from front matter of PDF files; Resolved DOIs via doi.org

Notes

- No specific licence was found for the SYR, only the general copyright statement on the main IPCC website

Summary

- AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023 (SYR): Copyright <https://www.ipcc.ch/copyright/>
- 3 Working groups reports (WGI, WGII, WGIII): Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/deed.en>
- 3 Special reports (SR1.5, SRCCL, SROCC): Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/deed.en>

Findings

Report	DOI full report	DOI resolves to	licence on landing page
SYR	10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/	https://www.ipcc.ch/copyright/
WG1	10.1017/9781009157896	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/climate-change-2021-the-physical-science-basis/415F29233B8BD19FB55F65E3DC67272B	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0
WG2	10.1017/9781009325844	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/climate-change-2022-impacts-adaptation-and-vulnerability/161F238F406D530891AAAE1FC76651BD	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0
WG3	10.1017/9781009157926	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/climate-change-2022-mitigation-of-climate-change/2929481A59B59C57C743A79420A2F9FF	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0
SR1.5	10.1017/9781009157940	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/global-warming-of-15c/D7455D42B4C820E706A03A169B1893FA	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0
SRCLL	10.1017/9781009157988	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/climate-change-and-land/AAB03E2F17650B1FDEA514E3F605A685	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0
SROCC	10.1017/9781009157964	https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/ocean-and-cryosphere-in-a-changing-climate/A05E6C9F8638FA7CE1748DE2EB7B491B	Creative Commons Attribution licence CC-BY-NC-ND 4.0

3. AR6 Citations / references: Bibtex downloads, reference count

Methods

- .bib-file count: Manual counting on website, needs revisiting
- Citations / references: Looked around for reliable sources

Findings

Report	Download Bibtex files	Bibtex file count	Reference count
SYR	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/ , no citations / references in this report?	0	0?
WG1	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/ , "Chapters" > "Downloads" > "Citations (bib)"	~13 .bib files	13.000-18.000, sources for these numbers see below
WG2	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/ , "TS"/"Chapters"/"Cross-Chapter Papers"/"Annexes" > "Downloads" > "Citations (bib)"	~29 .bib files	17.419, sources for these numbers see below
WG3	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/ , "Chapters"/"Annexes" > "Downloads" > "Citations (bib)"	~19 .bib files	?
SR1.5	https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/ , I don't seem to be able to find .bib files	-	5000-6000, sources for these numbers see below
SRCLL	https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/ , I don't seem to be able to find .bib files	-	7,800, sources for these numbers see below
SROCC	https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/ , I don't seem to be able to find .bib files	-	6,981, sources for these numbers see below

Sources for estimated reference / citation count per report:

WGI

- Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#WG1report
- The report's authors built on more than 14,000 scientific papers (says Wikipedia)
- over 18,000 citations including over 13,000 unique references, Analysis: <https://zenodo.org/records/7615825>
- 13,500 citations (says <https://www.carbonbrief.org/guest-post-what-13500-citations-reveal-about-the-ipccs-climate-science-report/>)
- 14,000 references (says <https://theconversation.com/234-scientists-read-14-000-research-papers-to-write-the-ipcc-climate-report-heres-what-you-need-to-know-and-why-its-a-big-deal-165587>)
- 19,266 distinct reference strings (says <https://zenodo.org/records/5475442>)

WGII

- Wikipedia:
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_2_report_\(impacts,_adaptation_and_vulnerability\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_2_report_(impacts,_adaptation_and_vulnerability))
- 17,419 DOIs cited (says <https://zenodo.org/records/6344388>)

WGIII

- Wikipedia:
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_3_report_\(mitigation_of_climate_change\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_3_report_(mitigation_of_climate_change))

Special Report: SR1.5

- Wikipedia
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_Global_Warming_of_1.5_%C2%BC
- The report, approved in Incheon, South Korea, includes over 6,000 scientific references, and was prepared by 91 authors from 40 countries (says Wikipedia)
- 5,099 distinct reference strings (says <https://zenodo.org/records/5475442>)

Special Report: SRCCL

- Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_Climate_Change_and_Land
- 7,828 distinct reference strings (says <https://zenodo.org/records/5475442>)

Special Report: SROCC

- Wikipedia:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_the_Ocean_and_Cryosphere_in_a_Changing_Climate
- report includes over 6981 cited references (says <https://www.centrescientifique.mc/en/article/the-special-report-on-the-ocean-and-cryosphere-in-a-changing-climate-srocc-accepted>)
- The 1,300-page report by 104 authors and editors representing 36 countries referred to 6,981 publications. (says Wikipedia)
- 7,161 distinct reference strings (says <https://zenodo.org/records/5475442>)

4. AR6 Authors count

Methods

- I did not actually count the authors - I relied on the number that was given on the landing page
- I did not consolidate duplicates, did not check for authors that have worked on more than one report

Report	Authors landing page	Authors count *	Authors tables **
SYR	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/ "Core writing team"	30	https://apps.ipcc.ch/report/authors/report.authors.php?q=38&p=
WG1	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/about/authors/	234	https://apps.ipcc.ch/report/authors/report.authors.php?q=35&p=
WG2	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/about/authors	270	https://apps.ipcc.ch/report/authors/report.authors.php?q=36&p=
WG3	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/about/authors	278	https://archive.ipcc.ch/report/authors/report.authors.php?q=37&p= (archived website)
SR1.5	https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/authors/	86	see link on the left
SRCLL	https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/authors/	107	see link on the left
SROCC	https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/about/authors/	~101	https://archive.ipcc.ch/report/authors/report.authors.php?q=33&p= (archived website)
Total		1106*	

* As mentioned in the text on the landing page

** Tables with authors' names, origin, gender, affiliation

5. Wikidata entries of AR6 reports

Methods

- Search in Wikidata for report name

Notes

- There are also entries for parts of the reports (e.g. the SPM for the SYR) in Wikidata. I have only listed full report entries, though.
- Collection in **Zotero**:
<https://www.zotero.org/groups/2437020/semanticclimate/collections/773CNPDW>

7. AR6 Figures count

Method

- Manually scanned and counted overview pages on the IPCC website, very unreliable numbers, need to be double-checked

Report	Landing page for figures	Figures count
SYR	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/figures	28
WG1	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures	~511
WG2	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/figures	~469
WG3	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/figures	~354
SR1.5	https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/graphics/#cid_6333	~89
SRCLL	Individual links off https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/ , I have not found a figures repository yet	~132
SROCC	Individual links off https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/ , I have not found a figures repository yet	~89
Total		~1672

8. AR6 Data count

No actual counting here, only some links:

World Data Center for Climate (WDCC)

- https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/q?general_key_ss=IPCC-AR6

On the IPCC website:

- Available Data for AR6 <https://ipcc-data.org/ar6landing.html>

IPCC Data browser

- <https://ipcc-browser.ipcc-data.org/browser/search?searchterm=ar6>
- <https://ipcc-browser.ipcc-data.org/browser/search?keywords=IPCC-AR6>
- <https://ipcc-browser.ipcc-data.org/browser/search?keywords=AR6>

Data and Code access (incomplete)

- WG1: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/data-access/>

9. AR6 Glossary count

Method

- Each PDF contains a 'glossary' section
- I did not count them individually, but looked at the general glossary repository on IPCC website for a total number

Glossary repository on IPCC website

- "You are viewing definitions of terms from the reports: AR6" <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>
- ca. 925 Terms in total

10. AR 6 report translations

Method

- Manually counting available translation files on website
- It's not always clear what is translated and what isn't
- Sometimes translations are announced, but not ready
- Numbers unreliable, need to be double-checked

Report	Landing page for translations	Translations count UN lang	Other lang
SYR	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/resources/translations/	5 in preparation	2 x SPM
WG1	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/translations/	5	2, partial
WG2	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/resources/translations/	5	3 x SPM
WG3	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/resources/translations/ Some translations here	5	1 x SPM
SR1.5	https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/download/ , "UN and other languages" Some translations here	5	4 x SPM
SRCCL	https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/download/ , "SPM in UN Languages", "SPM in other languages" Some translations here	5 x SPM	3 x SPM
SROCC	https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/download/ , "UN and other languages"	5 x SPM	5 x SPM

11. AR6 Acronyms

Method

- These numbers are rough estimates, I copied the lists from the PDFs and then manually corrected line breaks before I counted the lines. This is not accurate, and needs to be automated somehow

Report	available as HTML	Rough acronym count
SYR	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/annexes-and-index/#annex-ii	~90
WG1		~521
WG2	https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/chapter/annex-iii/	~692
WG3		~548
SR1.5		~566
SRCCCL		~430
SROCC		~194

12. AR6 Index terms

Method

- These numbers are very rough estimates, I counted/estimated them from the PDFs manually. This is BY FAR not 100% accurate, and definitely needs to be automated somehow
- I have only counted the main (bold) terms, there is a lot of subterms, sometimes hundreds of subterm for a main term

Report	Index count
AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023	~227
Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis (WGI)	~1138
Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability (WG2)	~1054
Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change (WG3)	~1005
Special Report: Global Warming of 1.5°C (2018) (SR1.5)	~526
Special Report: Climate Change and Land (2019) (SRCCL)	-1036
Special Report: The Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate (2019) (SROCC)	~477